

and slope ratio methods. These methods show that iodine and primary arylamine combine in a 2:1 molar ratio. The failure in getting colour in alkaline pH clearly rules out the possibility of oxidative coupling between aromatic amine and catechol and so it is regarded as charge-transfer complex. The charge transfer may be presumed to be taking place involving electron-transfer from the highest occupied π molecular orbital of the primary arylamine to the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital, π^* , of the semiquinone radicals as in the case of metol NBS reagent⁶.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium with Rubeanic Acid in Presence of Piperidine, Quinoline, α -Picoline and Collidine

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RUBEANIC acid in conjunction with different organic heterocyclic bases have been utilised to estimate Pd, Co and Ni^{1,5-7}. It has been found that piperidine, quinoline, α -picoline and collidine also enhance the colour and solubility of Pd(II) complex of rubeanic acid as a result of which rubeanic acid and one of the above four heterocyclic aromatic bases make a suitable ligand pair for the determination of palladium spectrophotometrically. Among the four bases studied, collidine is found to form the most effective ligand pair with rubeanic acid, the molar extinction coefficient in this case being distinctly higher than in other systems. The yellow colours which are developed

in the above four systems have been found to absorb maximally at 380 nm in case of piperidine and quinoline and at 410 nm in case of α -picoline and collidine. The optimum pH range has been found to be 7-10.5 in each of the four systems where Beer's Law is obeyed.

Experimental

Chemicals, reagents and apparatus: Palladium solution was standardised by dimethylglyoxime. A 0.1% solution of rubeanic acid was prepared in 95% ethyl alcohol. The solution was found to remain stable for several days. 10% solution of each, in distilled ethanol, were obtained from freshly distilled piperidine, quinoline, α -picoline and collidine (analytical grade).

All absorbance measurements were made with a Hilger-UVispek spectrophotometer. The pH values are determined with an Elico Model LI-10 pH meter, the later values being with respect to aqueous alcoholic solution.

Procedure: To a slightly acidic solution of palladium, free from interfering ions, 1 ml reagent solution (0.1% w/v) was added after the addition of any of the four bases for determinations with piperidine, quinoline, α -picoline or collidine. 2 ml piperidine, 5 ml quinoline, 3 ml α -picoline and 2 ml collidine were added before the addition of the reagent. The final volume was made up to 25 ml with distilled alcohol and the absorbance measured at 380 nm for piperidine and quinoline and at 410 nm for α -picoline and collidine. The results of the above investigations are represented in Table 1.

Composition of the complexes: The composition of the complexes as determined by Job's method of continued variation⁸ and molar ratio method⁹ shows that there are two different species with different heterocyclic base systems. While with pyridine and collidine, the presence of 1:1 metal:rubeanic acid ratio is observed, the 1:2 system seems to be predominant in other three systems (piperidine and rubeanic acid, quinoline and rubeanic acid and α -picoline and rubeanic acid). Bobtelsky and Eisenstadter⁹ found by heterometric titration and micro analysis of the dried product that palladium combines with rubeanic acid to afford a number of compounds having the composition Pd₂Rba₂, PdRba, Pd₂Rba₂ and PdRba₂ (where Rba=rubeanic acid molecule or its radical) depending on the pH of the medium during precipitation and the amount of reagent present⁹. In the present case the units containing one Pd ion (1:1 and 1:2 variety) seems to be stabilised by the additional ligation of heterocyclic bases.

The results of Job's method and molar ratio method of the four systems are represented graphically (Figs. 1-8).

TABLE-1

Metal ion.	Reagents	Beer's Law and optimum range	Sensitivity	Molar extinction coefficient
Pd ²⁺	Rubeanic acid and piperidine	1-8.4 ppm	0.017 μg Pd/cm ²	6246
Pd ²⁺	Rubeanic acid and quinoline	3-8.4 ppm	0.013 μg Pd/cm ²	8129
Pd ²⁺	Rubeanic acid and α-picoline	0.59-4.1 ppm	0.019 μg Pd/cm ²	5319
Pd ²⁺	Rubeanic acid and collidine	1.7-4.1 ppm	0.0104 μg Pd/cm ²	10211
Pd ²⁺	Rubeanic acid and pyridine	0.625-4.375 ppm	0.0148 μg Pd/cm ²	7224
		1.87-4.3 ppm		
		1-10 ppm ¹		

Fig. 1. Job's method of composition. Pd(II) Rubeanic acid piperidine complex.
Pd(II) = Rubeanic acid = $5.538 \times 10^{-4} M$

Fig. 3. Job's method of composition. Pd(II) Rubeanic acid quinoline complex.
Pd(II) = Rubeanic acid = $5.2875 \times 10^{-4} M$

Fig. 2. Molar ratio method of composition. Pd(II) Rubeanic acid piperidine complex.
Pd(II) = Reagent = $5.538 \times 10^{-4} M$

Fig. 4. Molar ratio method of composition. Pd(II) Rubeanic acid quinoline complex.
Pd(II) = Rubeanic acid = $5.538 \times 10^{-4} M$

Fig. 5. Job's method of composition. Pd(II) Rubeanic acid α -picoline complex.
Pd(II) = Rubeanic acid = $1.175 \times 10^{-4} M$

Fig. 6. Molar ratio method of composition. Pd(II) Rubeanic acid α -picoline complex.
Pd(II) = Rubeanic acid = $1.7625 \times 10^{-4} M$

Fig. 7. Job's method of composition. Pd(II) Rubeanic acid collidine complex.
Pd(II) = Rubeanic acid = $1.175 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Fig. 8. Molar ratio method of composition. Pd(II) Rubeanic acid collidine complex.
Pd(II) = Rubeanic acid = $1.7625 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Effect of diverse ions: Solutions were prepared in the same way as described under absorbance curve with 2.5 ppm of palladium(II) in each case containing different amounts of each ionic species whose effects were studied. It is observed that copper(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), platinum(IV), molybdenum(VI), vanadium(V), tungsten(VI), manganese(II) and chromium(III) interfered with the determination.

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Oxalylhydrazide: A New Reagent for Rapid Gravimetric Determination of Selenium

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THE growing importance of selenium in industry and chemistry is reflected by the large number of papers dealing with its determination by